

Surviving and Thriving in the Face of Workplace Adversity: Teachers' Morale at Universities

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Abstract

Although there is a growing amount of literature on how to survive and thrive in the face of workplace adversity, there is still a scarcity of research on universities teachers' morale. The current research aims to fill this gap in the literature by concentrating on the following concerns at the universities. It looked into the following existing literature in particular: the state of job-related factors at the universities; the level of teacher morale, as well as analyzing the relationship between demographic factors and teachers' morale at the universities; and the relationship between job-related factors and teachers' morale at the universities. Since the proposed study addressed university teachers' morale, the conceptual framework demonstrated the relationship between the variables. The study investigated demographic and job-related factors that impact university teachers' morale. According to the concept, demographic characteristics such as age, gender, highest academic credentials, marital status, and academic rank might impact one's work morale. Not only that, but job-related elements like as regulations, compensation, and incentives may all have an impact on employee morale, either individually or collectively.

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Workplace hardship is one of the major reasons that teachers and managers fail to succeed in their jobs and eventually leave education. The major causes of employment disasters in the educational setting are unfavorable and unsatisfactory elements of working conditions and the work environment, as well as the everyday challenges faced by teachers and managers in the academic milieu. University education is a critical step in the professional development of aspiring academics, presenting a variety of challenges and opportunities (Fernandez et al., 2019).

Prior to the founding of universities, European education took place in Christian cathedral schools or monastic institutions, where monks and nuns taught lessons for hundreds of years (Cobban, 1999). The forerunners of subsequent universities may be traced all the way back to the sixth century AD (Highfield, 1984). The University of Bologna, founded in 1088 AD, the University of Paris, founded in the mid-11th century, and the University of Oxford, founded in 1096 AD, were among the first universities. Pope Gregory IX, on the other hand, formally acknowledged the University of Paris in 1231. (Olaf, 1997). Durham University, founded in 1832, 600 years after Oxford and Cambridge, was the third university to open in the United Kingdom, and it was followed by London University four years later, in 1836. (Kasozi, 2009). In the 12th century, the Cole Cathedral in Paris became the foundation for Northern Europe's oldest university. As a result, the first university tradition may be traced back to Christianity (Sheehan, 1978).

Oxford began at the start of the next century under the sponsorship of King Henry III in 1248 AD and evolved into a mature institution in the late 12th century (Sheehan, 1978). Education was practiced at all levels in pre-colonial settings on the African continent (Lulat, 2005). Famous Islamic colleges such as Karawiyyinn in Fez (Morocco) in 859 AD, Al- Azhar University in Cairo Egypt in 970 AD, and Sankore University in Timbuktu in the 12th century were among them. The oldest continually functioning university in the world is Al-Azhar University. Islamic Religious Education was a popular course at Muslim colleges. Many parents, particularly those from the upper socioeconomic strata, pushed their children to enroll in specific courses. Poor children, like their parents, were superstitious during the time, and so were unlikely to value university education (Okebukola, 2002).

In Africa, university education began in the 1960s, at which time several African countries gained political independence. These universities, on the other hand, were modeled after European universities (Assie- Limumba, 2005). The exploitation of Africa's riches was the emphasis of European imperialism in Africa (Tiberondwa, 1998; Nangoli, 1988). As a result, the goals of the education system they built, particularly at the higher education level, were to further this aim. As cited in Kayindu (Mutebi, 2005; Kwandwo, 2003; Whitsett, 2001; Tiberondwa, 1998; Chaube and Chaube, 1996), this was accomplished by producing colonial agents and workers (equipped with reading, arithmetic, and writing skills, especially at the lower levels) to man the colonial administrative machinery (2011). This higher education system was mostly scholarly, and it served as a reserve for the offspring of current African elites, much like medieval university education. Rather of replacing the old African education system, it coexisted with it at first. It produced a small number of graduates who were specially trained to work in the colonial government. As a result, they were able to secure official pay jobs in the colonial government soon after graduation. The university education system was in balance in the sense that the number of graduates was proportional to the number of available job opportunities, and university education met current labor market demands. The employment of graduates was guaranteed. Academic staff morale was ensured through employee motivation, university rules, and incentives in order to meet the objectives.

The two-factor theory is significant in that it argues that job satisfaction is determined by extrinsic factors and motivators. Employee morale will be studied using demographic and job-related characteristics as independent variables. According to the equity hypothesis, job happiness is a result of the benefits one receives for his or her labor in comparison to what others in similar companies receive. This is significant in that certain academic employees may find the conditions at their individual institutions to be satisfactory or dissatisfactory, depending on the situation at other universities or organizations. Theory X and Y are significant in the sense that certain academic officials may utilize authoritarian managerial tactics in the management of universities since theory X assumes that individuals are typically lethargic and should be compelled. Because of theory Y's assumptions, which explain that individuals are not fundamentally lazy but can practice self-direction, other authorities utilize democratic and team management approaches.

Academic staff, often known as university instructors, are university personnel who are responsible for academic-related activities. Dissemination of knowledge (teaching and assessing pupils), research, and publication are examples of these activities. Teaching assistants, lecturers, assistant professors, associate professors, and professors are the different types of teachers. The morale of academic staff (teachers) will be examined in this study based on their job performance, the rate of turnover, the level of attendance, and the degree of complaints. This is because, when all other circumstances are held constant, good attendance and low staff turnover are indicators of high employee morale (Azabo, 2018). Employee morale indicators were used to assess the morale of university instructors (Maicibi, 2003; Lloyd, 1992; Kreitner & Kinich, 1995; Maicibi, 2007; Mamoria & Gankar, 2002; Lock, 1992). Teachers' morale indicators included the following ten factors: teachers' level of performance, dons' or teachers' research and publications, the rate of teacher turnover, the grievance phenomenon in the University, dons' feelings about the University, dons' feelings about the reward system, dons' real feelings, behavior at work, and feelings about the University's procedures or rules.

Employee turnover refers to the number of people who quit a company to work somewhere else. It has to do with whether or not people stay at their current jobs for a long time before looking for work elsewhere. If the employee turnover rate is significant, it is assumed that the employees are dissatisfied with the company (Kreitner & Kinick, 1995; Loen, Mosley & Pietri, 1989).

Employee performance refers to how well individuals carry out their responsibilities at their various workplaces (Lewis, Thornhill & Saunders, 2003). In general, strong staff morale correlates with good performance, and vice versa. The performance of university instructors will be measured in this suggested study using the primary functions of a university teacher. Since universities are meant to be knowledge factories, university instructors' duties include spreading knowledge (teaching and assessing students), doing research, and publishing articles in journals and books (Manyasa, 2006). The study looked at how much the academic staff or dons at the University of Juba do all of the following. We may deduce if their performance is very good, good, bad, or extremely poor based on this.

Employees typically file grievances when they consider anything in the organization/institution to be unfair or harmful. In general, a high number of employee complains indicates poor staff morale, and vice versa (Maicibi, 2005). The current study looked at the severity of these grievances (whether very high, high, low or very low) to infer

(whether their level of morale is very high, high, low or very low). Because employee morale is influenced by a variety of factors, the present study focuses on two of them: employee demographic characteristics and job-related factors, to see how they affect teacher morale at the University of Juba. Age, gender, degree of education (academic credentials), marital status, employment experience, and academic rank are among demographic characteristics that influence an individual's personal life and position. These elements frequently have an impact on one's mood (Luthans, 1998; Lock, 1992).

Workplace-related variables are those characteristics of the job that have an impact on how workers view work and the company, and therefore on their performance and morale. The current study focuses on five of these factors: dons' perceptions of the University's ethical atmosphere, their salary, welfare, and working conditions, as well as university regulations. In most cases, the better these elements are, the higher staff morale will be, and vice versa (though under a few circumstances it is not the case as claimed by Mamoria and Ganker, 2001). Salary, financial incentives, and non-financial incentives are all part of the income condition.

The current study aims to achieve the following objectives based on the aforementioned discussion and dilemma: I investigate the state of job-related factors in universities, (ii) assess the level of teachers' morale in universities, (iii) establish the relationship between demographic factors and teachers' morale in universities, and (iv) investigate the association between job-related factors and teachers' morale in universities. Based on the aims, the current study raises the following issues, which will be answered by systematic investigation: (a) How are job-related aspects in universities currently? (b) How do university instructors feel about their jobs? (c) Does there appear to be a link between demographic variables and university teacher morale? & (d) Does there appear to be a link between job-related variables and teacher morale at the Universitis?

Literature review

Salary, incentives (financial and non-financial), and relationships with colleagues, leadership (management), business regulations, and corporate culture are only a few of the variables that influence people's work. Individuals anticipate to obtain the desired result if they behave or perform specific behaviors in a given way. It's critical that, in addition to delivering significant outcomes, staff think they can complete the duties. If the aim or goals do not appear to be reached in their eyes, they will become less motivated, which will result in a drop in performance. As a result, identifying the main elements that motivate employees is the first and most crucial step in increasing performance. As a result, employees should be appropriately compensated (Azabo, 2018). The fair reward system is based on distributive and procedural fairness concepts. This is also expressed by Eliot Jaques in accordance with the idea of "fairness." These remarks demonstrate that if the payment system feels fair, it will be fair. The following hypothesis supports this theory: there is an unrecognized fair standard of remuneration for every level of work; people at work share unconscious knowledge of norms; remuneration should correspond to the level of work and personal abilities; employees should not be paid less than they deserve when compared to colleagues. This idea appears to have been transferred into the common language of reward managers. It is occasionally employed as the final choice criteria in job categorization, and it has the potential to override the findings reached by analytical job evaluation exercises (also known as the "felt-fair test"). Such tests risk reinforcing preconceived notions about relative function values (Armstrong, 2006).

Transactional incentives are represented by the top two quartiles, which include salary and perks.

These are pecuniary in nature and are required for staff recruitment and retention, but they are easily imitated by rivals. The relevant (non-monetary) rewards of the lower quartile, on the other hand, are required to raise the value of the top quartile. True power emerges when firms mix interpersonal benefits with transactional rewards, as Thompson (2002) pointed out. Individual recognition, success, responsibility, independence, influence, and personal growth are all rewarded through cooperation incentives (non-monetary). It established the notion of the reward connection, which refers to intangible incentives associated with the workplace (quality of work and life, work-life balance, recognition, performance management, learning and development). People may be rewarded for their hard work by having chances to improve their skills and employability in the workplace. Employee training may be intentionally designed by supporting, coordinating, and monitoring their learning in the workplace. Today, many employees regard training to be a significant element of their total pay package (Pearce & Robinson, 1988). The performance management method is a good approach to give out appropriate incentives. It can serve as the foundation for a healthy psychological contract by defining the shared expectations of superiors and their workers. Feedback might provide you with ideas. With the proper support from leaders and organizations, performance evaluation may be used to plan personal growth and foster self-management learning.

Growth possibilities, according to Alderfer, are critical for rewarding and encouraging employees.

"Satisfying developmental needs is contingent on who he is and what sort of person he can become," he explained. People may be given this chance by an organization by providing them with a variety of experiences and training to enable them advance to higher levels of responsibility. It has the ability to provide brilliant people with the advice and support they need to realize their full potential and find a rewarding profession that matches their talents and aspirations. It is feasible to control how people are rewarded for their professional advancement (Pearce & Robinson, 1988).

The importance of an organization's fundamental values as the foundation for establishing an empowering work environment has been acknowledged, according to research by John Purcell and colleagues at the University of Bath. The most successful businesses have "big ideas," according to experts. He has a clear vision and an intrinsic, permanent, collective, quantifiable, and manageable value system. They have to do with sustaining productivity and adaptability. There is a definite link between good attitudes toward satisfaction, motivation, commitment, and operational performance with human resource policies and procedures. Managers play a crucial role in reward administration. They exist to guarantee that individuals get things done, to ensure that tasks are completed, and to establish and maintain constructive and helpful relationships with team members. Recognition through feedback, the scope of relevant measurements, the feeling of responsibility, and possibilities for growth through on-the-job learning and training. They are important to the effectiveness of the performance management process and can trigger or have a significant impact on emergency payment choices (Pearce & Robinson, 1988). "The phrase employee opinion is increasingly used to describe all procedures and structures that are directly and immediately connected to the decision-making of the firm," according to Peter Boxall and John Purcell. Workers can have a say in these partnerships as part of the usual working interaction between supervisors and employees.

Theoretical framework

The dual factor theory, often known as the motivational factor hygiene theory, was introduced by Frederick Herzberg in 1959. Two categories of variables, cleanliness and motivation, impact job performance and hence job happiness, according to this hypothesis. This study's hygiene elements are related to the work environment. This suggests that an employee's motivation is influenced by their surroundings, but if they are unsuitable in the workplace, employee discontent will result. They are sometimes referred to as external factors since they attempt to motivate employees from outside of the workplace, such as company policy, management, oversight, working conditions, personal relationships, wages, status, job security, and personal life (Flippo, 1984; Fombrum, Tichy, and Devenna, 1984; Greenberg and Baron, 1989; Bruce and Pepitone, 1991; Harsey and Blanchard, 1993; Armstrong, 2000; Subba-Rao, 2001; Mullins, 2002; Duening and Ivancevich, 2003). Job happiness is not based on hygiene issues. When they understand that their fundamental maintenance requirements have been satisfied, they will eventually feel indifferent. These characteristics do not make individuals healthy or strong; instead, they keep employees from getting contaminated by bad attitudes about work or the workplace. In other words, while hygiene issues are not the root of employee contentment, they must be addressed first in order to establish a happy workplace (Maicibi, 2003).

Stimuli such as professional challenges, responsibilities, performance or advancement possibilities, and acknowledgment, on the other hand, assure contentment. These are related to the work and are intrinsic or distinctive to each individual in their own way. When there are no stimulation elements at work, individuals are not always unhappy, according to Herzberg's two-factor hypothesis. However, because the job itself does not indicate a shift in motivation, a person cannot sense any satisfaction. People will feel as much satisfaction as feasible when the motivating component is inherent in work, stimulating or maintaining the energy of labor. Only such a person, according to Herzberg, can be motivated consistently (Dollipon, Ferris and Studd, 1995; Frost, Vance and Walter, 1997; Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 2002). As a result, this theory was chosen since the dependent variable in the current study is teacher morale, and the independent variables are demographic and work-related elements that impact it. In theory, these characteristics may be used to develop a personal work ethic.

The X-theory and Y-theory proposed by MacGregor Douglas in 1960 were also influenced by this study. People must be threatened with control, compulsion, and punishment, according to Theory X, since they are self-centered, sluggish, and loveless at work. It also thinks that ordinary people want to be led, avoid taking on too much responsibility, have modest goals, and, most significantly, seek security. Workers, on the other hand, are not innately lazy, according to Theory Y, and may learn to take responsibility and practice self-direction and self-control if they are dedicated to corporate goals. The majority of individuals do not dislike labor by nature. Work is as natural as playing and sleeping in terms of putting physical and mental energy into it. Threats and punishment from the outside aren't the only ways to drive efforts toward achieving company objectives. In order to attain what they believe they desire, people use self-direction and self-control. The advantages of achieving a goal have an impact on dedication to the goal. The principal incentive, the demand for contentment and self-actualization, can be a direct result of an organization's goal-oriented activities, according to Theory Y. Humans are not born with irresponsibility, a lack of ambition, or a preference for safety. Under the appropriate circumstances, ordinary people must learn not just to accept but also to seek responsibility.

The theory also assumes that imagination, creativity, creativity, and the ability to use these qualities to solve organizational problems are widespread among people (Date, 1969; Greenberg, 1990; Wagner & Hollenbeck, 2002; Mejia and Balkin, 2002; May, Korezyriski and Frenkl, 2002; Daft and Marcic, 2004; Liao, 2005). Some philosophers such as John Locke (1632-1704) agree with Theory X and believe that by using it, organizational goals can easily be achieved. However, other philosophers such as John Amos Komensky and Jean-Jacques Rousseau supported Theory Y. For them, forcing people to act or perform can be disastrous. This seems to mean the application of different leadership styles in an organization such as indifference, conformity, dictatorship, status quo, teamwork, opportunism and paternalism, as well as the control or manipulation of external factors. This can lead to employees feeling different levels of satisfaction. In choosing this theory, the author realized that it had some loopholes, such as the lack of explanation of the situation where coerced workers and workers who are free in the workplace sometimes or do not show expected behavior. Despite this weakness, the researchers believe the theory is relevant to this study. The researchers also believe that it is one thing to hypothesize and another to correct the hypothesis, so the current research is being conducted. Stacy Adams' Equity theory is also instrumental and significant in this regard. According to this theory, employees judge in comparison to other people in the same or different organizations whether the rewards they receive are appropriate based on their input (time, effort, training, experience). If they think their rewards are unfair, it can lead to dissatisfaction (Koontz and Weihrich, 1998; Barry and Rhonda, 2002). The relevance of this theory is that if staff at one university feel that their rewards are unfair compared to others at other universities or related organizations, they can ask management to change direction if management is indifferent and authoritarian. This theory has some weaknesses such as that employees value their own contributions and receive rewards for the contributions and rewards of other recipients, and employees put their own interests before the interests of the organization, which makes comparison challenging. Second, the theory focuses on rewards, as if rewards are the only thing that makes employees happy. Despite these loopholes, the theory is relevant to research.

This research will also be based on organizational behavior theory and expectation theory as they are directly related to the research variables. The theory of organizational behavior was proposed by Getzels and Guba in 1957. According to this theory, the behavior observed in the organization is a function of the interaction between the organizational dimension and the individual (individual or ideographic). Therefore, in order to understand or assess the behavior of an office-holder (head or official), it is necessary to underpin the organizational dimension of his behavior (i.e. what the organization demands of him, what is expected of him or what is expected of him) and personal dispositions, such as the personality and the needs / needs of the individual (Hakman, Lawler and Porter, 1983; Pecora and Austin, 1989; Robins, 1996; George and Jones, 1997; Heneman, Schwab, Fossum and Lee, 2000) as reported by Kayindu (2011). The importance of this theory in this research lies in the assumption that due to certain factors such as personal demographics, university administrations typically employ certain employee-oriented, organization-oriented, or both employee and organization management techniques.

Victor Vroom's expectation theory examines the influence of expectation on behavior. Vroom believes that the effort a person shows in their work depends on two expected components. How likely is it that the expectation or performance will be rewarded in the outcomes of a sense of achievement, money, promotion, and recognition? The other thing that he pointed out is the degree to which a person attaches importance to the expected results. The gist of the theory is that a person must perform certain actions in order to achieve their desired goal.

To make this choice, the individual weighs the likelihood that the behavior or performance will enable them to successfully achieve their goal. If he expects a certain action to be successful, he is more likely to choose that behavior. This is what Vroom calls the "potential for rewarding effort" (Babalola and Ademola-Atanda, 2006). Thus, if teachers expect a good return on potential investment (e.g. time, energy, effort), they tend to increase their work ethics.

Figure-1: Proposed framework

Conceptual framework shows the linkage between the variables of the proposed study since the proposed study will address university teachers’ morale; the study will explore the demographic factors and the job-related factors, which influence the morale of the university teachers. The framework thus suggests that the demographic factors namely age, gender, highest academic qualifications, marital status, and academic rank can influence one to have high or low morale at work (Maicibi, 2007). Not only that but also the job-related factors, namely the policies, salary, and incentives can either individually or altogether influence on employees’ morale. The extraneous variable mean or imply that the morale of university teachers is not only influenced by demographic and job-related factors but also by other factors like the respect they wield in society, political factors, such as the security of their lives and property. Given the many wars South Sudan have been engaged in, the security of people’s lives and property matters and can contribute to their university teachers’ high or low morale at work. The proposed study will however not address extraneous variables with regard to the way they influence employee morale, which call for further future endeavors to comprehend the phenomenon.

Hypothesis development

Morale is the degree of enthusiasm and spirit with which people work as a group or team to perform the organizational activities. It may be high or low. High morale reflects satisfaction towards the work, financial and non-financial incentives associated with the job (work), willingness to cooperate with others and collective group effort or high performance for attainment of group goals.

Ethical behavior means the behaviour conforming to generally accept social norms concerning beneficial and harmful actions. This is expected of all organizational employees. Ethics, morals, and values are expected of all university teachers in performing their tasks. Ethics is a branch of philosophy that deals with the rightness or morality of human conduct. The word ethics also relates to the objects of human conduct in certain areas such as medical ethics, business ethics, professional ethics etc. Values are cultural standards of behavior that acts as guides to businesspersons in setting and pursuing goals. Thus, businesspersons use values in making ethical judgments whether they realize it or not. More and more business managers are being challenged to increase their sensitivity to ethical problems. They are pressured to evaluate critically their value priorities to see how these fit with organizational and societal realities and expectations (Buhler, 2002; Armstrong, 2006).

Research by Kayindu (2011) also shows that projects with educational qualifications (p-value 0.001) have a significant correlation with job satisfaction, academic ranking (p-value, 0.005) and the number of years in the current position (p-value) have, 0.000). Specifically, it shows that doctoral students are more satisfied than other civil servants with lower qualifications are; the professor's satisfaction with externalities is higher than with other academic degrees and the higher his position, the more satisfied he is. These results are not isolated. They agree with the results of Ssesanga (2003) that Ugandans are generally satisfied with the real aspects of their work. The P-value of an individual's position is 0.220, which indicates that the position of an academic official does not significantly affect his / her job satisfaction (Kayandu (2011). This means that different academic officials have different positions. Just like the deans) the dean, deans, auxiliary deans and department heads are satisfied with it due to their function as academic administration at the university, the contractual nature of their work and the salaries and bonuses usually shared between them. A study of work ethic and job satisfaction (Kaindu (2011), seen by academic leaders, supported by research by Malimakisesi (1998); Mugabyomu (2006); Namubiru (2007); Mugizi (2007)). The concept of equality has a profound impact on how employees normally interact with different aspects of corporate life. This is also in line with the findings of Olaniyi-Owolabi (2007) and Kamagala (2005) that work experience (regardless of job experience) is closely related to job satisfaction and emotional and regulatory engagement. to organize. Because a good and healthy work experience motivates and motivation has a lot to do with work. Related methods are Knut Fisher (2000), Weiss (2002), Tso and Liu (2005).

Measuring employee performance is important and usually depends on their morale. Measurement is an important concept in performance management. It is the foundation for providing and generating feedback, determining where something is going well and indicating that it is not going well, and lays the foundation for continued success so that corrective action can be taken. For those responsible for achieving quantitative goals (like sales), measuring performance is relatively straightforward. For knowledge workers (like scientists) this is even more difficult. However, if you differentiate between two forms of result output and result, this difficulty is reduced. Output is the result that can be quantified

and the result is the visible effect of the effort, which is not necessarily quantifiable. All functions have components that are difficult to measure as output. However, all actions produce results even if they are not quantified. This makes it necessary to measure performance against results that can be expressed qualitatively as achievable standards or levels of competence. It is therefore important to answer this question when setting or agreeing a goal: "How do we know that this goal has been achieved? Alternatively, exceed a quantifiable goal, complete the project or task and other results satisfactorily, or achieve the agreed level of performance in this form or the level of performance specified by the provider.

Salary is one of the most important aspects of work. Musaazi (2005) pointed out that employees can be motivated and reached when they receive adequate remuneration through remuneration. A well-designed and managed 'Pay for Achievement' policy will help provide an effective mechanism to reinforce successful behavior, a clear focus on what is really important to the organization, the primary vehicle for cultural change in the organization and a cost management mechanism. An organization's payment system is also very important in order to achieve several main goals, such as ensuring the best productivity and a high quality level of production.

Another study by Ong and Teh (2012) on the internal reward and performance system of Malaysian commercial banks found that most commercial banks offer cash and in-kind rewards; the introduction of the reward system is not influenced by the age and size of the organization. However, the study found that there is a negative correlation between external rewards and the financial performance of the organization, while internal rewards correlate positively with the financial performance of the organization. Kikoiko (2014) examined the effects of the reward system on the organizational performance of the Tanzanian banking industry using the example of a commercial bank in Mwanza City, Tanzania. In the study, 65 employees from three commercial banks (CRDB, NBC, and NMB) in Mwanza City were interviewed with a self-filled questionnaire. I also interviewed selected employees. The result is a significant correlation between the incentive system of the Tanzanian banking sector and organizational performance: the case of a commercial bank in Mwanza City, Tanzania. However, this research was not conducted in South Sudan, so this research is needed. RibaunKorm (2011) examined the relationship between salary and performance of Cambodian civil servants (CCS). They interviewed some Cambodian government stakeholders, including central government employees, education administrators, teachers and school administrators, and showed that wages are either the most important, or at least the most important factor in performance, or are negative. Job performance leads to dissatisfaction with civil servant positions. However, salary has little or no effect on motivating people to seek employment in the public service, and it does not encourage employees to perform well. On the contrary, respondents named factors such as job security or lifelong work, social status and prestige, future personal growth and other opportunities, and career as motivating factors for performance. Salary is the single most important factor preventing civil servants from doing their job well. This relationship between wages and performance has also been explored through the application of motivational theory, with the exception of expectation theory, which performed relatively poorly in the Cambodian case. The performance of CCS was also examined in the context of organizational culture and policy, and it was found that both had a significant influence on behavior.

Corresponding results were obtained in a research carried out in Uganda. In Massibi (2003), for example, it went against Kampala, Mukono, Mubindi, Mbeji, Kibuga, Masaka, Jinja, Mbarara, Vakiso and Luero. The results showed that external incentives such as annual salary and allowances have increased. (PTA) Pay workers to improve their performance (Massie,

2003: 52). Therefore, motivation is an aspect of every manager because it brings about ideal behavior and good performance in the organization. This is no different from Turinway (2011), who examined the reward system, job satisfaction, organizational engagement and employee performance in Ugandan public universities. The study examined the relationship between reward systems, job satisfaction, organizational engagement and employee performance for teachers, employees and managers in public higher education institutions in Uganda. 300 participants from two Ugandan institutions, Kyambogo University and Makerere University Business School, took part in the study. Pearson's correlation results show that there is a statistically significant positive correlation between the variables (reward system, job satisfaction, organizational engagement, and employee performance). Regression analysis shows that about 38% of changes in employee performance are due to the reward system, job satisfaction, and the company's commitment to using the reward system as a key indicator of employee performance. Similarly, Nairuba (2011) examined motivational practice and teacher performance at Jinja Municipal Middle School in Jinja District, Uganda. In particular, the research aims to determine the nature of working conditions and the impact of additional benefits provided through incentives on the performance of middle school teachers. Use the Pearson Correlation Coefficient to establish the relationship between middle school motivational practices and teacher performance. The research shows that wages and salaries have no direct impact on teacher performance. The results of the study showed that 70.9% of respondents (average 3.56 points) stated that additional benefits such as allowances, recognition, promotion, and appreciation still depend on the availability of funds and the opinion of management. These benefits will affect the teacher's performance if paid after the work is completed. In some institutions, working conditions are still favorable, which has an impact on the actual performance of the school. Therefore, good working conditions are suitable for the performance of all employees in any organization. The research also shows that there is a weak correlation between motivational practice and teacher performance: the Pearson's correlation coefficient is -106, the coefficient of determination is 0.0112, and the fixed level is 1.12%. This means that there are many other factors that can affect the teachers' performance. A recent 2017 study by Asiimwe of private primary schools in the Kampala area found that teacher performance as measured against national primary school performance was tested for four consecutive years, ending in 2013, 2014, 2015 and 2016. The reason is responsible for the salary of good teachers, other factors are school management, material resources and school culture. Finally, the impact of rewards on employee performance cannot be underestimated. Several studies have been conducted to determine the factors that affect teacher and employee performance in any organization. There is a lot of literature on the many factors that affect an employee's performance in any organization, but these factors vary from organization to organization and tend to change from time to time (Kigenyi, 2017). Findings and conclusions differ on the relationship between economic incentives and teacher performance. Bennell and Akyeampong (2007) pointed out that teacher performance is very important, suggesting that poor teacher performance (in the form of slowdowns, absenteeism, and insufficient preparation) affects the quality of teaching, learning outcomes and social Seriously impaired development. Akiri and Ugborugbo (2009) pointed out that teacher performance determines the quality of education, which means that poor performance harms quality and therefore development as learners drive the national development agenda. A study by Salman, Muhammad, Ogunlad, and Ayinla (2012) showed that most teachers and students believe that poor teachers' salaries in terms of salary and bonuses affect their performance, resulting in collective failure among Ondo students leads. State of Nigeria: Although relevant, South Sudan is not mentioned, so it is for this study. Another study by Engellandt and Riphahn (2004) in Switzerland came to the conclusion that unexpected bonus payments are an effective motivation for employee efforts. Ahn and Vigdor

(2010) found similar results in the United States, suggesting that economic incentives motivate teachers to work harder. A similar study by Charity & Timinefere (2011) found that economic rewards have a significant positive impact on employee performance in Nigeria, even if their rewards are not specifically geared towards teacher performance. Gungor (2011) conducted a study in Turkey and the results showed that economic rewards have a positive impact on employee performance. Yamoah (2013) shows that there is a significant correlation between teachers pay and work performance in Ghana. Another study conducted in Ethiopia found that the lack of incentives such as rental and transportation subsidies can affect teachers' job performance (Negussie, 2014). Therefore, the University of Juba will conduct a study to assess the veracity of these claims.

Adkins (2004) conducted a study on teacher performance compensation in Florida, USA, which found that most teachers disagree with whether teacher performance compensation is an incentive for teachers to work harder. A similar study conducted in Kenya by Njanja, Maina, Kibet, and Njagi (2013) found that cash rewards had no impact on employee performance. A study conducted by Uzonna (2013) in Cyprus concluded that growth opportunities, recognition, and non-monetary rewards require financial incentives such as fringe benefits, wages, bonuses, pensions, and profit sharing to achieve optimal employee performance. Effective motivational factors are better than performance pay.

Much of the literature on the relationship between economic reward and work performance shows that economic rewards and incentives can have a positive impact on teacher performance in some locations but not elsewhere. This means that managers should not mistakenly assume that all employees are motivated by the same things and rewards (Garba and Bello, 2017). Therefore, managers need to properly understand and describe the incentive effects of these rewards or incentives (Kigenyi, 2017). Robbins (2003) supports this view, pointing out that in an organization, some employees may work harder to get a promotion and raise, while others may just be appreciated. The fewer schools there are, the more difficult it is to hand out rewards. This means that before implementing a reward plan, administrators need to understand the motivation behind motivating each employee, as not all employees are motivated by the same needs and rewards. They should be treated differently because of differences in employee characteristics in terms of gender, marital status, sexual orientation, experience, number of children and seniority (Robbins, 2003).

In Uganda, a survey carried out by Masibi (2003) showed that school initiative is a very important factor in good performance. The Macibi research includes teachers from three universities and schools in Kampala, Wakiso, Mapigi, Mukono, Luwero, Jinja, Mubende, Kiboga, Masaka and Mbarara. External incentives such as bonuses and allowances motivate teachers to improve their performance. finished. This shows that many public secondary schools in Uganda have financial incentives, but their governance is sometimes not determined by performance measurement. Researchers affected by USE fundraising activities believe that many school strikes and poor performance are the result of poor relationships and lack of motivation between teachers and school principals. The existence of such incentives in Uganda does not mean that they also exist in South Sudan, so research is recommended.

This is in line with the results of Moses (2016), who indicated that some secondary schools have differences in the application of reward systems and that these differences have resulted in teacher performance not meeting expected results. This revelation also shows that not all teachers receive the same rewards. For example, Moses (2016) also reported that

performance-based financial incentives could motivate teachers to perform better, while school principals are not motivated by the same incentives. According to research by Moses (2016), tiered monetary incentives are the most commonly used incentives for the schools they choose, but there are also other incentives, such as welfare incentives and promotion. Research by Moses (2016) shows that economic rewards have a positive impact on teacher management and performance. Thanks to these incentives, absenteeism by teachers, supervision, and the early completion of courses could be reduced. It also shows that there has been an increased commitment to tutoring homework, lesson plans for slow learners, the general improvement in the work culture of teachers, and their enthusiasm for the classroom.

From the literature discussion it can be concluded that financial incentives and other reward systems are intended to solve two main problems: on the one hand, to motivate the performance of teachers and, on the other hand, to attract and retain outstanding teachers for teaching. Teachers in most Ugandan schools are rarely effectively screened for increases by their line managers. Instead, the system automatically relies on personal services and qualifications and managerial responsibilities recognized by the Ministry of Education and Sport. However, critics of traditional remuneration systems such as Kituyi, Musau and Thinguri (2014) argue that such programs are unfair to highly motivated and efficient teachers who are not rewarded for their extra efforts.

DEST (2007) supports the above view that the lack of financial incentives for excellence may be the main reason for teachers to leave the teaching profession and those who have a variety of employment opportunities outside of the teaching profession. Consistent with this view, Armstrong (2009) shows that rewarding money is a powerful driving force directly or indirectly related to the satisfaction of many needs. For example, why teachers prefer currency symbols; difficult economic times, financial freedom, etc. Armstrong (2009) further pointed out that wealth in itself may not be intrinsic to the individual, but since teachers can help achieve many intangible goals, it is a tremendous driving force. Horner (2009) believes that high performing employees who add value to the company must recognize their efforts, value and contribution through appropriate rewards. Proactive teachers who are passionate about the quality of school performance are an important asset of any school. Every effort should therefore be made to maintain this, including the establishment of an attractive financial incentive system in the school. Completely.

Another reason for the Korean War of Liberation of 1910-1945 was the poor working conditions of the workers. For example, many Koreans were employed in rice plantations and colonist-owned industries. The Namibian War of Liberation was also due to poor working conditions. For this reason, the indigenous people of Namibia founded the Ovamboland People's Organization and the Southwest National Federation to fight for human rights. In Ethiopia, until 1974, certain groups of landowners owned most of the land. Most of the farmers have no land, which forces many people to enter the informal labor sector under poor conditions. Farmers / tenants should give 50% of their products to landlords. This led in part to the Ethiopian Revolution in 1974. Other revolutions with worker prejudice include the Algerian Revolution of 1954, the Guinea-Bissau War of Liberation (1963-1974), the War of Mozambique (1964-1975), and the Zanzibar Revolution of 1964 (Ketelbey, 2002). As Kayindu (2011) pointed out, the above opinions suggest that poor working conditions for workers are unsatisfactory for workers and can have disastrous effects. Work-related factors can include corporate culture and values, leadership style, and communication. These can also affect the morale and thus the performance of teachers or workers.

Schein (2010) pointed out that management with a poor organizational culture lacks transparency and frequent communication across the company. In a weak organizational culture, the behavior of the employees does not match the organizational priorities due to insufficient communication and a lack of uniform leadership by the management (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). When the organizational culture is weak, the very existence of the organization is jeopardized because the members of the organization have different values and beliefs and because they can run counter to the priorities of management.

Loyal and dedicated employees are essential to maintaining an effective corporate culture and improving corporate performance. Pinho et al. (2014) pointed out that employees with personal responsibility can significantly improve the performance and productivity of companies. When employees feel self-reliant and responsible, they can carry out their duties without close supervision and control (Denison, 1990). Project managers can use their time to focus on other priorities in the organization.

A strong organizational culture plays an important role in adjusting the current and future direction of the organization (Raza et al., 2014). On the contrary, poor or ineffective management of corporate culture can affect profitability and productivity. In a weak organizational culture, it is difficult for employees to define the values of the organization and determine the right process for carrying out projects in the organization (Childress, 2013). Project Management Skills Skill is the ability to carry out project management activities at the expected level of performance. Project management shows the performance of individuals in completing tasks and provides technical skills to complete the project in terms of scope, time, cost and quality. In the context of project management, this management skill is used to share project information with others and, due to the very technical and detailed nature of the work, it needs to be done effectively. Research shows that project managers deal with complex ideas and large amounts of information. In addition, they must continuously coordinate between multiple organizations and stakeholders and work within the constraints of the contradicting relationship between full project ownership and limited formal authority (Shahzad et al., 2012).

Therefore, the researchers believe this study bridges the void in the literature search. These gaps relate to time and context as well as content.

The following alternative hypotheses were developed.

H1: *There is no direct positive relationship between demographic factors and teachers' morale in the Universities.*

H2: *There is a positive relationship between job-related factors and teachers' morale in the Universities.*

H3: *There is a positive relationship between thriving at work and teacher's morale in the Universities.*

H4: *Thriving at work is related to important employee outcomes*

Conclusion:

The current study seeks to address this gap in the literature by focusing on the following university issues. It looked at the condition of job-related variables at universities, the level of teacher morale, as well as assessing the link between demographic characteristics and teachers' morale at universities; and the relationship between job-related factors and teachers' morale at universities. The conceptual framework established the link between the variables since the planned study focused on university instructors' morale. Administrative

universities, education officials, school owners, non-governmental organizations, academics, and other researchers will benefit greatly from our study framework. It will inform public education policymakers about initiatives to boost the morale and effectiveness of higher education instructors. Furthermore, the framework of this study will give education policymakers with sufficient and improved chances to actively encourage teachers, eliminate negative incentives, and promote more favorable views toward teacher morale and performance.

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